

Chapter 2: Who is your audience?

When designing a participatory online concert, we may wish to define our target audience. To this, an array of factors can be considered, such as: age group, gender, level of experience with music (and/or with a specific style of music), language, location, access to technology, specific set of skills, experience in a specific area of knowledge, among others.

The set of a target audience will work hand in hand with the strategies for recruitment. For example, a call for participants in English may, by itself, filter recruitment to English speakers primarily.

Also, the place where the call or invitation will be placed, could be tailored according to age group as well. For example, some social media platforms are more seen by one age group than another. Also, posting calls for participants in places such as schools or cultural centres may, by itself, channel the recruitment to specific groups which may be distinguished by age, location, gender, areas of interest or social backgrounds.

Additionally, the technology required to participate in the project can also be an element that will determine the group to be recruited. For example, in the *music as an invitation* project, the initial idea was to run the online workshops via the platform Zoom. However, one of the potential participants could only participate using her mobile phone, since she did not have a computer, neither access to wireless connection at home. Considering that it could become complicated for her to download a new software using her mobile data, I decided to do the workshops through Google Meet instead, which was a platform which she had used before in her mobile phone and was more familiar with.

Naturally, these factors and other factors may be taken in account besides the content and visuals of the advert.

After the recruitment, a possible step is the selection of participants among the ones who have responded to the call/invitation. The selection can take place for a number of reasons, including: capacity, required skills / knowledge, confirmation of eligibility of the prospective participant according to the criteria of the project, among others.

Case study 1: *music as an invitation* (year 1: 2023-2024)

The project *music as an invitation* had a gender aspect in its proposal, therefore the call to participants was directed to adult women (first year of the project) and girls age 13 - 17 years old (second year of the project).

One of the first learnings in the recruitment process of the first year of this project, was regarding the definition of gender. After sending out the first version of the poster with the call for participants, I have received the questions:

‘Are you including anyone identifying as a woman (i.e. also trans women) in your call for women participants? What about non-binary people?’

Therefore, for this project, the call for participants was updated with the note: ‘all self-identified women are welcome’. ([Illustration: Call for participants](#))

The posts were in English and in Portuguese, which also framed the target audience.

The recruitment was done through posts on social media channels, which included my Instagram and Facebook pages, as well as my host university’s. The recruitment was also forwarded by other musicians and music promoters which were part of my network.

This decision ended up mostly attracting participants which were already in contact with the my work. This factor incidentally created a group already inclined to engage in an intimate creative process, which was indeed a positive aspect for the proposal of the project.

The recruitment did not ask for any further selection, since it naturally ended up with 14 active participants - which was within the expected group size.

Case study 2: piece *Hecate writes* & concert *rsvp: piano, toy piano, electronics, and actions*

The recruitment of participants for the second year of the *music as an invitation* project focused on groups of teenage girls from Norway, Brazil, and the UK. The decision for such a age was part of the agenda of the project regarding gender inequality and empowerment of voices traditionally neglected in the field of classical music. Since this project could have included some postings on social media, the specification of the minimum age, 13 years old, took in consideration the requirement for access to some of the most popular social media platforms such as Instagram and Facebook. On the other hand, the maximum age, 17 years old, tried to ensure that all the participants were approximately in the same phase of adolescence.

The language of the recruitment was English and Portuguese, which naturally filtered the call to participants who could speak either of these languages.

The recruitment was firstly made by sending emails to school and private piano teachers, also to NGOs and social programmes dedicated to development of girls. In this process, different contact persons asked for different (and sometimes contradictory) adjustments to the invitation text and additional materials such as:

- broader texts with more details about the activities involved in the project
- a more succinct text with just a general call
- a poster with attractive visuals and less text
- a poster with more textual information about the project

On one hand, these adjustments shows the need for the tailoring of the recruitment to each context. On the other hand, it might have given a hint about the most appropriate strategy for each project, since the contacts who asked for more modifications in the call / invitation ended not being very productive in attracting participants anyway.

In the meantime, calls on social media were also posted, which did not bring much results either. [\(Illustration: Call for Participants - EVEVEVE\)](#)

For this phase of the *music as an invitation* project, the most effective recruitment came through contacts with friends and individual invitations to their teenage daughters. The adjustment of the recruitment strategy coincided with the change of the method. Now, instead of developing a whole concert with the participants, it was decided to focus on the development of the music which had been commissioned for the project - *Hecate writes*, by Alwynne Pritchard. The delimitation of the location was also amended, now including France as well.

In this process of inviting potential participants individually, I would firstly get in contact with the parents explaining the project and asking if they would like to pass the invitation on to their daughters. After they had told the girls about the invitation, if the girls were interested, I would book a video call to tell them about the project and the activities in more detail, giving them a chance to have an informed decision about their participation in the project.

As for the live streamed concert *rsvp: piano, toy piano, electronics, and actions*, besides advertisements to the general public, I got in contact with specific audience members, most of them musicians and artistic research practitioners. I explained them the participatory activities which would take place during the concert. Having this informed group was indeed helpful to encourage other audience members to engage with the participatory proposal. Among other actions, the participatory activities of the concert included walking around in the room while playing a sound with their mobile phones, as part of one of the pieces of the programme.

[\(Illustration: photo\)](#)